

Center for Composite Materials

Role of Modeling and Simulation in the Development and Application of Digital Twin for Liquid Composites Molding Processes

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Outline

- Liquid Injection Molding
 - Process and Process Variations
- Digital Twin Role in Process Control
 - Possible Constructions of Digital Twin
- Simulation Approach, Uses and Capabilities
- Connecting the Digital and Physical
 - Direct Full Model Simulation as a Part of Digital Twin
 - Note on Machine Learning Approaches
- Real Time Challenge

LCM (RTM) Manufacturing Process

Variety of Processing Methods

Variety of Process Variants

Flexible Infusion Settings

Lots of Ways to Do It Wrong:
Numerical Simulation
Helps with Choices

Flow Variability: Race-tracking

Transverse
racetracking
in ribs

Racetracking along
mold walls

Transverse racetracking
in tapered regions

Ribs cut too short

Source: Uneven Spacing and Gaps
Impact: Changed Flow Patterns
Prevention: Difficult

LCM Process Variability: Racetracking Impact

- Same Part Being Infused, Different Outcomes Possible Depending on Gaps
- This Phenomenon Cannot Be Prevented
- The Racetrack Must Be Detected and Identified
- Corrective Action Must Be Taken
- Reason to Deploy AI in Some Form

Resin Infusion Designed in Absence of Racetracking Channels:

Effect of a Single Racetracking Channel on Flow:

Digital Twin Idea

Physical Part Manufacturing

Create Model

Updates of State

Suggested Controls

Accurate Digital Representation


```
001000011001110  
110111011011000  
10101010000000  
011110110011111  
01110100010101  
01001010101001  
100111000110011  
110000000_
```


Early Attempts on Digital Twin

Simulation:
Always the Same Result

Note:
Needs Work on Feedback,
Physical World Sabotages This!

**Symmetry in Problem not Reflected in
Solution!**

Requirements to Be of Use

Physical Setup

- Sensor System That Can Provide Feedback before Process Is Finalized
- Some Control Option to Reverse Negative Development as Directed by Digital Twin

Digital Twin

- Sufficient Accuracy of Model Description
 - Inclusion of Any Uncertain Aspects as Parameters to Be Modified on the Fly!
- Ability to React (Update Model as Needed) to Parameter Changes/Feedback in *real time*
 - This Includes Finding Some Solution

Possible Approaches to Building Digital Twin

- Tweak Some Controls
- Observe Outcome
- Machine Learn from Physical Mistakes
- **This is Prohibitively Expensive!**

- Run Realtime Process Simulation if You Can
- Add Some Control/Solution Search Algorithm
- **Base Control on Gradual Reduction of Uncertainty in Model**

- Run Process Simulation with as Many Disturbances, Control Actions and So On
- **Feed This To Machine Learning**
- **Use AI to “Do” Digital Twin**

Connected: We Need Simulation!

Simulation Development and Uses (1)

Initially:

Process Design,
Injection and Venting
Strategies

Outcome:

Sufficiently Accurate
Model
Simulation Time
(Lower Fidelity) in
Seconds

Injection Location=>
Flow Patterns=>
Last Separate Regions to Fill=>
Vent Location

Injection Lines=>
Flow Time and Patterns=>
Sequential Injection Location
And Timing

Simulating Controlled Injection Into Complex Part

Notes:
- Injection lines modeled by 1D elements
- Side lines open when flow reaches them (reaction to sensor tripping)

Distribution Media layout
=>
Lead Length(s)
=>
Delay Lines, Gaps and
Timing

Simulation Development and Uses (2)

Handling Process Variations and “Features”:

RTM Model
Expanded to VARTM,
CRTM, Pulltrusion

Model Can Handle
Distribution
Channels, Fabric
Deformation, etc.

Simulation Development and Uses (3)

Handling Process Variability:

Modeling Individual Disturbances

Generating Multiple Scenarios
“Automatically”

Sufficient Throughput
to “Have Them All”

- Material Properties Vary
- Placement and Cutting Inaccurate
- Flow Patterns Change
- Infusion Scheme Needs to Change

- Number of Possibilities
- Statistical Probability for Each
- Modeling All Scenarios, Processing the Output
- Automation Needed

IFAB Solution:

Process Control and Sensing

To Use Simulation for Digital Twin It Must Allow Control of Model Process

- Simulation of Sensor Action Needed!
- Implementation of Control Elements (Say, Additional Gates) Needed

Simulation Based Process Design

No Control

Filling Simulation:

Manufactured Part:

Active Control

Filling Simulation:

When racetracking detected, inject:

- #0: 0.0
- #1: Q_0
- #2: $1/3 Q_0$
- #3: 0.0
- #4: Vent

Manufactured Part:

Simulation Capability Available for Digital Twin Development

- Most Liquid Composite Molding Processes Can Be Satisfactorily Modeled
 - Performance is *Very Acceptable* even for Large Number of Possibilities
 - Variations of LCM Processing Have Been Addressed
 - Modeling Extra Distribution Hardware (Tubing, Distribution Media) Has Been Fully Resolved
- Process Variability Has Been Addressed. Disturbances Based on Part Geometry Have Been Successfully Generated
- Control Actions Can Be Designed and Modelled
 - Approaches Vary, Generic Recipe Still Ahead (Space for ML Here)
 - Actual Implementation Remains Task for Digital Twin Development

Communication Between Simulation and Outside World

What Is Needed to Use Simulation On-Line Within Digital Twin

- Simulation Flexibility to Change Settings Mid-Way of Run
- Mechanism for Digital Twin Code to Send Commands to Simulation
 - Change the State of Parameters As Needed (Determined from Physical Realm)
 - Modify Simulation State on the Fly Including Injection Control Option(s)
- Mechanism to Transfer Simulation Data Between Executed Programs
 - This Can Be Used to Chain Other Models "In" as Needed (Volatiles, Heat....)
 - It Can Facilitate Parallelization

Current LIMS Approach Through MPI Interface:

MPI Connectivity and Coupling LIMS Simulation with Additional Process Physics Models (Volatile Transport)

**Properly Resolved
Communication (In This Case
over MPI) Broadens the Process
Model Applicability**

Conclusions

- The Construction of Digital Twin for LCM Requires Process Modeling
 - Either Directly or to Train AI
- Process Model Must Handle The Usual Trappings of LCM Processes (Most Do)
- Process Model Must Simulate Process Variability (Most Do)
 - To use On-line Modeling, The Model Parameters Must Be Accessible *During* the Simulation (LIMS Allows This)
- Process Model Must Simulate Control Action (Some Do)
 - To use On-line Modeling, The Controls Must Be Accessible *During* the Simulation (LIMS Allows This)
- Important Features for Actually Using Simulation are Inter-Process Communication and Computational Performance

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